

**SOME CHALLENGES FACED BY EFL STUDENTS ON WRITING
SKILL**

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Abstract: English is an international language and in demand today. English is by far the most widely used language around the world. However, English language writing has always been a challenge for second language students to master. Developing students' ability in writing is one of the major challenges faced by the EFL teachers in most educational institutions nowadays. Thus, this study aims to explore the challenges faced by both the students and teachers in learning as well as teaching writing skills in higher education.

Keywords: Writing skills, teaching and learning writing, challenges, educational institution, English as a Foreign Language.

In teaching English, the teacher aims at developing four abilities – ability to understand, to speak, to read and to write. The ability to write occupies the last in this order, but it does not mean that it is least important.

Regardless of whether the language being learned is a first, second, or foreign language, it is said that writing effectively and expressively is the most challenging of the four skills. Even though they can hear and comprehend spoken English, students may misunderstand grammar and sentence structure when writing in the same language.

According to White, writing is not a natural activity. All people have to be taught to write. Like speech, writing needs constant practice. Bell and Burnaby point out that writing is an extremely complex cognitive activity in which the writer is required to demonstrate control of a number of variables simultaneously. At the sentence level, these include control of content, format, sentence structure, vocabulary, punctuation, spelling, and letter formation. Beyond making a sentence, the writer must be able to structure and integrate information into cohesive and coherent paragraphs and texts [2, 231].

Only when they have sufficient pre-communication input, a topic to write about, and a clear idea of what they want to write can students begin to learn how to write. In fact, developing writing skills necessitates deliberate practice and effort in idea development and analysis. Students may find it challenging to write clearly in a second language because the tenses and sentence structures in their native tongue may differ.

Compared to students writing in their native languages (L1), students writing in the target language (L2) is a bit more complicated as they need to acquire proficiency in writing strategies and in following the techniques in the use of the language as well [8, 111].

It is true as Gagne, reported that “writing is a highly complex activity with many component processes...requiring the acquisition of both declarative and procedural knowledge and a conceptual understanding of the nature and purpose of writing” [1, 314].

Young learners experience writing problems at two levels. These include problems with lower level skills, including grammar, punctuation, capitalization, handwriting, and spelling. At the higher level, the problems include audience awareness, content generation, planning, revising, and the knowledge about the topic. Flower and Hayes identified two fundamental but very demanding problems that writers face during the composing process: the knowledge problem and the communication problem. On the one hand, writers must produce an organized set of ideas for a paper by selecting and arranging a manageable number of concepts and

relations from a vast body of background knowledge and experiences. On the other hand, writers must fit what they know to the needs of the reader and the constraints of formal prose [4, 21]. They basically need to demonstrate knowledge and understanding of story components, language skills, vocabulary, mechanics, conventions of print, audience needs and characteristics, and an ability to focus on abstract topics. Writing also calls for meticulousness in the choice of vocabulary and the ability to set out a coherent chain of ideas.

Writing as a skill is not imparted at the tertiary level, yet, the principal skill in which the students are tested is writing. The typical writing classroom is dominated by a product oriented approach. Students are given a ready-made essay or composition which they reproduce in the examination. Persistent writing problems, therefore, make it difficult for students to reach their educational, occupational, and personal potential. Eventually, struggling writers have little awareness of the writing process and have underdeveloped skills and techniques in addition to the fact that they are teacher-dependent. Struggling writers need to practice writing by doing exercises which involve copying from a text or reproduction of learned material in order to learn the conventions of spelling, punctuation, grammatical agreement, and the like. They should be engaged in a variety of activities of controlled nature.

Writing is therefore considered a skill that is not mastered easily, but acquired gradually as a result of considerable changes in a writer's basic composing skills. The learner should improve his/her knowledge about writing and practise self-regulatory or strategic behaviour. It should be remembered that writing is a personal activity that can be practised outside the classroom too. Along with these, if there is motivation and persistent effort, individuals will move from novice, to competent, and then to expert writers.

Writing is at the centre of academic experience and at certain levels it extends beyond that too. Language teachers are faced with the job of assisting students to write well. Historically, when writing was explicitly taught in higher education, the emphasis was on students' writing as final texts or 'products'.

Teaching writing – whether in formal writing classes or as an activity within discipline-based courses – often entailed presenting students with models of good writing, and asking them to imitate those exemplars. Often, little analysis occurred of the various rhetorical aspects of the texts or the social contexts in which the texts functioned. The focus instead was on specific features of the written texts: for example, spelling, text structure, vocabulary and style. In addition, little attention was typically paid to the process of writing, including the conscious and unconscious decisions that writers make in order to communicate for different purposes and to different audiences. In an era in which students may have been more homogenous and shared previous educational experiences and social backgrounds, the assumption was often made that students could pick up how to do academic writing through this process of imitation. There is an abiding concern with the nature of students' composing processes, and how teachers across the grade levels might more effectively gear instruction to individual needs, backgrounds, and interests. Hence, process oriented instructional approaches have become common, with teachers providing opportunities to brainstorm ideas, complete initial rough drafts, receive peer and teacher feedback, and revise and proofread [7, 48].

In order to teach effectively, a language teacher should have the following language-specific competencies. These include the ability to do the following kind of things:

1. To comprehend texts accurately To provide good language models
2. To maintain use of the target language in the classroom To maintain fluent use of the target language
3. To give explanations and instructions in the target language
4. To provide examples of words and grammatical structures and give accurate explanations
5. To select target-language resources (e.g., newspapers, magazines, the Internet)
To monitor his or her own speech and writing for accuracy
6. To give correct feedback on learner language

7. To provide input at an appropriate level of difficulty
8. To provide language-enrichment experiences for learners

Grammatical errors in writing is another problem teachers identify among students while teaching writing. Teachers often face problems with sentence formatting and grammatical requirements needed for writing to be coherent. Activities and practice material focusing on recognizing and using words with the correct spelling are key elements of instructing students in English.

Explicit writing instruction must be integral to the course, as part of the course content and as a significant, recurring activity. Through instruction, students should learn about writing, including its structures and functions, and should practise writing in a variety of modes and settings appropriate to the discipline. The forms and types of writing instruction that will be used in the course should be explained in the syllabus or supporting teaching materials.

According to Hyland, an emphasis on language structure as a basis for teaching writing is typically a four-stage process:

1. Familiarization: Learners are taught certain grammar and vocabulary, usually through a text.
2. Controlled Writing: Learners manipulate fixed patterns, often from substitution tables.
3. Guided Writing: Learners imitate model texts.
4. Free Writing: Learners use the patterns they have developed to write an essay, letter, and so forth [5, 73].

The goal of writing instruction can never be just training in explicitness and accuracy because written texts are always responses to a particular communicative setting. Ostensibly, students are unwilling to write because of the anxiety they have about their ability to construct sentences and paragraphs. Therefore, as Harmer (2004) says, “with students like this who lack familiarity or confidence with writing (or need enthusiasm for it), we need to spend some time building the writing habit – that is

making students feel comfortable as writers in English and so gaining their willing participation in more creative or extended activities'

Given the challenges posed by the teaching-learning process of writing, language teachers should be well-prepared to face them. Before the commencement of the class, the teacher should ask himself / herself the following questions:

1. What level are my students? Why are they taking this course?
2. Do they need writing skills for specific reasons? (business correspondence, college application letters, etc.).
3. What do you expect them to produce? (a short email for beginners; an essay for an examination).
4. What is the focus of the exercise? (structure, tense usage or vocabulary).

Once the teacher gets a clear idea about the skills students need to develop, the next step is a wide variety of writing tasks that may be assigned to students to help them hone their writing skills. But careful consideration of the questions answered above should help the teacher narrow down his / her options and begin to focus on how to involve the students in the activity thus promoting a positive, long-term learning experience. As in correction, the teacher must choose the most appropriate manner for the specified writing area. If formal business letter in English is required, it is of little use to employ a free expression type of exercise. Likewise, when working on descriptive language, attention to writing skills might be given to presentation and coherence of points.

In every language class, the teacher plays a great role in making the writing tasks as achievable and productive as possible. The teacher should:

- Make the written tasks a frequent occurrence to reduce anxiety around them;
- Make the tasks meaningful to students personally and in general;
- Give appropriate teacher feedback and give the students a chance to revise their drafts (as this promotes self-correction and noticing). Feedback should focus on improving the students' work, not correction for correction's sake;

- Give the students time to reflect on the writing process (what worked, what didn't, what was enjoyable, etc.);

- Do not always grade the tasks; students should not be writing solely for credit Establish real-life situations to engage the students (i.e., set up an email pen pal system between another school, etc.).

Above all, the teacher should know that a learner might know how a language ought to be spoken or written without any flaw, but only when he is able to use it in a real context it can be understood that the individual is a master in it.

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